
Application of Sentinel 2 and -3 satellite images for the monitoring of suspended matter in the extremely dynamic Ems estuary

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Abstract: The Ems estuary features historically high turbidity values. Monitoring of the effect of measures to improve the transparency is desirable, however, doing this by traditional sampling is impossible because of the continuous variation as a result of tidal changes and river inflow. Therefore, we test the possibilities of combining innovative high frequency point observations with satellite images. The satellite images are used to observe SPM at scales of 10 and 300 m pixel size over the whole area, while the high frequency observations of a WISPstation instrument and a turbidity sensor are used to record the temporal dynamics at a point station. Additionally, high frequent spectral observations of water reflectance were used to test and calibrate atmospheric correction algorithms for the satellite-based SPM maps, with the goal to automatically process time series maps for monitoring purposes. The concentrations derived from WISPstation, satellite match-ups, and in-situ observations were compared to each other for validation. Generally there was a good match between results from both satellites and the WISPstation, although it appeared that the selected atmospheric correction method, C2RCC, lead to different corrected reflectances in the most turbid areas, and therefore also different concentrations. Forcing the atmospheric correction on the WISPstation results was used to quantify the differences and is a possible solution for the issue. The WISPstation and turbidity sensor time series show the large variations in the concentrations due to tidal and seasonal changes, which explains the need for very short time differences for match-ups. The maps provide a great insight in the spatial dynamics caused by variations in tidal effects. Although additional work is needed for the most turbid areas, the tested methods together provide a very good insight in the spatial-temporal dynamics of this estuary, and can be applied in operational monitoring of this and other complex coastal areas.

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1. Introduction

The estuary of the Ems (Figure 1) is very turbid. Especially in the most inland part, called Dollard, total suspended matter (SPM) concentrations are often $> 100 \text{ g m}^{-3}$, and frequently also $> 200 \text{ g m}^{-3}$. Even 'fluid mud' is known to occur in the area [1], in which SPM can reach tens to hundreds kg m^{-3} [2]. The Ems discharges in the Wadden Sea, an intertidal flat area sheltered from the North Sea by a line of islands.

The Ems estuary was added to the already existing Natura 2000 areal of the Wadden Sea in 2016. The appointment as a nature area required additional monitoring of the ecological and chemical status, next to already existing requirements, e.g. for the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD). Phytoplankton is an important indicator for water quality, and it determines together with phytobenthos a large portion of the primary production – and with that the carrying capacity of the area. Turbidity – in the Wadden Sea largely

caused by SPM, is the main limiting factor for primary production in the Wadden Sea (e.g. [3,4]), and therefore the sometimes extremely high turbidity has a large impact on the Natura 2000 goals of the Ems estuary.

Capturing the spatial and temporal dynamics in the Wadden Sea and Ems estuary with manual point samples is very difficult and not cost-efficient due to the high spatial and temporal variability. The effects of tide and currents, freshwater inflow versus seawater inflow, depth, and seasons create a complex and dynamic situation [5]. Satellite imagery might be the solution to capture the spatial variability. This was recognized when, after an extensive study on monitoring status and needs [6], the outline of the international monitoring program was published [7]. Earth observation (EO) was mentioned as an important means to obtain insight in the spatial distribution of phytoplankton (measured as Chlorophyll-a, Chl-a) and turbidity.

Although EO data has been used to monitor algal blooms in oceans for decades (since the launch of the Coastal Zone Scanner in 1978), application of EO data in coastal zones and especially estuaries is still under development. The main issue for operational application in coastal zones were the spatial and temporal resolutions of the available satellites, which did not match with the fine scales of an estuary. For example, the dedicated MERIS instrument on Envisat still had 300 m pixels, which is relatively large in a tidal flat area such as the Ems estuary, and the temporal resolution was every 2-3 days. Possibilities for the application of EO data for coastal zones and estuaries have increased significantly with the ESA optical Sentinel satellites (since 2016), that provide a high, up to 10-meter resolution via Sentinel 2 (S2) and almost daily imagery via Sentinel 3 (S3). S2 data was already used for mapping benthic biomass on surfacing mudflats in the Ems area [8].

However, it is known that atmospheric correction (AC) methods for the new S2 and S3 satellites for water surfaces are not yet fully developed (e.g. [9]), leading to inaccurate water quality parameters. AC is an essential step in the processing of raw satellite imagery, especially for deriving water quality parameters, because the light reflected from the water (the signal) is much smaller than the effects of cloud and atmosphere ('the noise'). About ~45% of the amount of sunlight is lost on the way to Earth [10], while a similar reduction can be expected on the way back to the satellite. In the open ocean, AC models can assume a zero reflection from the water in the near-infrared (NIR) spectral bands, caused by the high absorption of near-infrared light by water molecules itself. Any light captured by the satellite in the NIR in deep, clear waters is therefore reflected by the atmosphere, which makes it easy to correct for. In coastal and inland waters there are substances dissolved in the water, such as SPM, that reflect NIR light, while other substances, such as coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM) absorb NIR light (e.g. [11]). AC models for coastal zones are therefore complex, and often based on neural-networks or bio-optical algorithms. Both of these are sensitive to their original training or tuning dataset, which makes application in other areas not always possible.

Therefore, in this study an adjusted method for AC is tested, in which the results of the most suitable AC model are corrected with a factor that was derived from direct matchups with situ reflectance measurements from a WISPstation. When unexpected low concentrations were found in the most turbid areas, the surface reflectances from the WISPstation were used to force an AC on a number of matching images, to compare the behavior of the chosen AC method in the most turbid areas and to demonstrate a potential solution.

The WISPstation also delivers high-frequent concentration measurements. SPM concentrations from EO and WISPstation are compared with the those from a submerged turbidity sensor and in situ data from the national monitoring program (mwtl) for consistency. Some examples of the application of EO and WISPstation data to analyse the spatial-temporal dynamics in the Dollard are presented.

Figure 1. Map of the Ems Dollard estuary with the in situ locations indicated.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Satellite data and pre-processing

In total three years (2017-2019) of satellite data was downloaded and processed for the Ems-Dollard area. Level 1C S2 MSI data were downloaded from the Copernicus SciHUB, level 1C S3 data were downloaded from EUMETSAT for the first years and for the later periods from the Copernicus SciHUB.

Studies on the applicability of atmospheric correction methods for this area ([12]) learned that the C2X processor lead to the best results for comparisons for pixels to ground-truth data, closely followed by C2RCC. Since C2X leads to noisy maps and to be consistent between the two satellite instruments, for S2 the IdePix processor as applied for cloud flagging ([13]) followed by C2RCC ([14]) for atmospheric correction, and for S3 IdePix was combined with the updated version of C2RCC that corrects for calibration issues of the sensor. S3 was processed at its native resolution of 300 m, S2 was processed at a resampled resolution of 10 m.

Comparison of the resulting water leaving radiance reflectance values with ground-truth data learned that C2RCC was overcorrecting S3 for the atmosphere for this area ([15]). Therefore, after atmospheric correction a band-wise correction to compensate for the average error in the AC was applied ([15]). In practice, that meant that for S3, band $q_w 708.75$ that is used to derive TSM, was multiplied with 1.10587. For S2, the series of match-ups to retrieve a compensation factor was too small ([15]), so the S2 data was not corrected.

Land, and, more importantly in this area: surfacing tidal flats, were removed by the water index. The water index was based on reflectance on top of the atmosphere (r_{toa}). For S3, pixels for which:

$$((q_w 560 - q_w 865)/(q_w 560 + q_w 865)) > 0.2, \quad (1)$$

and for S2, pixels for which

$$(r_{toa}560 - r_{toa}842)/(r_{toa}560 + r_{toa}842) > 0.2, \quad (2)$$

were labeled as 'water'.

In a later stage, when it appeared that unrealistically low concentrations were seen in the most turbid areas (in the Dollard), the AC was forced based on a WISPstation reading. The reflectance at the water surface measured by the WISPstation was subtracted

from the reflectance on top of the atmosphere (TOA) measured by S2 or S3 for the pixel in which the WISPstation was installed. The difference was assumed to be ‘atmospheric effects’, and these atmospheric effects were accordingly subtracted from each pixel in the image. This was done using the WISPstation reading that was closest in time to the image acquisitions. This was done for 2 days for which there were S2, S3 and WISPstation data acquired within a short time, to server as an example of an alternative AC method.

2.2 Continuous turbidity and water level sensors and processing

The Dutch national monitoring agency Rijkswaterstaat (RWS) has a permanent measurement pole installed at Lat 53.474324, Lon 6.821572, close to Eemshaven. At this pole are various sensors installed, including a turbidity sensor (YSI 6600 V2) at a fixed depth of -3.5 meter NAP, and a water level sensor. Both data series were requested at 10-minutes intervals. For this, the actual data that was measured every minute were averaged between 5 minutes before and 4 minutes after the recorded time.

2.3 WISPstation reflectance data

The WISPstation ([16]) is an automated optical instrument to measure water-leaving reflectance from buoys and fixed locations. It uses two sets of sensors in a carefully chosen configuration to measure the light reflecting from the water for the full visible and near-infrared spectral range: the down-welling radiance from the $L_{sky}(\lambda, \theta)$ in which θ is 42 deg from the zenith, the total upwelling radiance $L_u(\lambda, \theta)$ at 42 deg from the nadir ($\theta = 138$ deg) and the downwelling irradiance $E_d(\lambda)$. One set measures towards the North North-East and one set measures towards the North North-West. It automatically selects the set that produces results without sun glint.

The water leaving radiance reflectance $L_w(\lambda, \theta)$ is calculated according to

$$L_w(\lambda, \theta) = L_u(\lambda, \theta) - \rho_{sky} * L_{sky}(\lambda, \theta), \quad (3)$$

in which ρ_{sky} is the air–sea interface reflection coefficient, which is standard set to 0.028 [17]. The remote sensing reflectance (Rrs) is calculated as

$$Rrs(\lambda, \theta) = L_w(\lambda, \theta) / E_d(\lambda), \quad (4)$$

From the reflectance it can determine the concentrations of e.g. Chl-a, SPM, cyanobacterial pigment, the presence of scums and transparency. The WISPstation sends its measurements over 3G or 4G to WISPcloud, which processes the measurements, applies a first quality check and makes the results available via an API. The WISPstation was installed at the measurement pole close to Eemshaven, and set to measure every 15 minutes in the period November 2018-December 2019.

2.4 In situ data from regular monitoring

In situ SPM data (g m^{-3}) measured by RWS was obtained via <https://waterinfo.rws.nl>. For the selected years, monitoring data was available for the stations Rottumerplaat 3km (53.56611, 6.56417) - monthly, Huibertgat Oost (53.55913, 6.66120) - every 2 weeks in summer and monthly in winter, Bocht van Watum (53.33493, 6.94394) – every 2 weeks in summer and monthly in winter, and Groote gat Noord – every 2 weeks in summer and monthly in winter (53.30429, 7.15666).

2.5 Calculation of SPM from satellite, WISPstation and continuous turbidity sensor data

From the spectral datasets (S2, S3 and WISPstation), SPM was calculated with an algorithm based the 705 nm band from [18], but slightly different per instrument to adjust for the difference in band settings. Good validation results between S3 data and in situ (mwtl) data were obtained within H2020 CoastObs (unpublished), so these settings were fixed to:

For S3:

$$\text{SPM} (\text{g m}^{-3}) = 561.94 * \rho_{w708.75} / (1 - \rho_{w708.75} / 0.1892), \quad (5)$$

As explained earlier, band $Q_w708.75$ was multiplied with 1.10587 to compensate for the error in the AC before entering the SPM equation.

For S2:

$$\text{SPM (g m}^{-3}\text{)} = 493.65 * Q_w705 / (1 - Q_w705/0.18753), \quad (6)$$

For the WISPstation:

$$\text{SPM (g m}^{-3}\text{)} = 493.65 * Q_w705 / (1 - Q_w705/0.1879), \quad (7)$$

Rrs was converted to Q_w by multiplying Rrs with π , and Q_w705 was calculated as the average between 700 and 710 nm.

For the continuous turbidity sensor, RWS provided a conversion factors based on comparisons between turbidity and laboratory SPM measures of 2.2 for total SPM, leading to:

SPM from the turbidity sensor:

$$\text{SPM (g m}^{-3}\text{)} = 2.2 * \text{Turbidity (NTU)}, \quad (8)$$

For S2, S3 and the WISPstation SPM values that were calculated as < 0 were removed, for the WISPstation also values > 500 were removed. For the WISPstation, shading of the E_d sensor by the measurement pole or shadow of the pole on the water measured by the L_u sensor would lead faulty reflectance measurements and unrealistically high concentrations. For the turbidity sensor from the measurement pole, time series showed that between late August and early September 2019 the values varied between very high and invalid. Measurements from this period and other measurement labeled as invalid were removed.

2.6 Correlations

The turbidity sensor and the WISPstation were both located at the permanent measurement pole for the year 2019. To compare with the satellite data, pixel extracts from this location were made from S2 and S3. To avoid noise, the S2 pixels were extracted from a 3×3 pixel window and averaged. S3 pixels were extracted at their original resolution of 300 m. The mwtl in situ stations are located at different locations, so comparisons could only be made with pixel extracts of the EO data at those locations. Mwtl samples were taken from a ship, and always during the same tidal phase (e.g. at Groote Gat Noord it must be high tide to allow the ship to reach the area). Because the overpass times of the satellites are always around the same times for each sensor, there were barely any appropriate matchups (simultaneous sampling and satellite overpass, during cloud free weather). For the scatterplots, a matchup window was defined as plus or minus $\frac{1}{2}$ hour (e.g. maximum satellite 30 minutes before in situ or the other way around), although arbitrarily seen the large fluctuations in concentrations during such a period.

2.7 Time series analysis

The high-frequent data from the continuous turbidity sensor and the WISPstation are used to visualise temporal pattern, e.g. those related to tide and those related to seasonal changes.

2.8 Mapping

The spatial maps of the satellite imagery are used to visualise spatial patterns, e.g. those related to tide.

3. Results

3.1 Correlation between the datasets

Figure 2 shows the correlations between the data from the two satellite sensors, the WISPstation and the continuous measurement pole; the trend lines are forced through 0. A few outliers (as indicated in the graphs) are ignored for the trend lines. The SPM values

from the WISPstation and the two satellite sensors are lower than the SPM measurements from the measurement turbidity sensor. The plot of the WISPstation versus the SPM derived from the turbidity sensor is more noisy than those of the satellites (a lower R2). S3 and the WISPstation follow almost the same relation with the turbidity sensor (both have 0.39 as slope), while S2 shows somewhat lower concentrations (slope of 0.28).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 2. Relation between SPM derived from the two satellite sensors, the WISPstation and the turbidity sensor. For the (a) and (b) trend lines are composed without the indicated outliers. (b) is the same as (a) but zoomed in without the outliers. (c) shows the relation between the SPM concentrations derived from match ups (max 30 min difference in time) of the two satellite sensors at the location of the measurement pole.

There is a good correlation between the SPM values derived from the two satellite sensors, at least for the – less turbid – location of the measurement pole (Figure 2c). This plot confirms that the values derived from S2 are generally lower than those of S3.

In theory, pixel extracts from the satellite based maps can be compared with the in situ monitoring data from the mwtl locations. However, it appears to be difficult to find suitable matchups (< 30 minutes difference) with the in situ samples. Those are sampled by boat; the timing is based on the tidal phases and therefore not linked to the satellite overpasses. An example of a ‘matchup’ with satellite data is shown in Table 1. On this day, there were two overpasses of S3 and one by S2. Even though this was a ‘lucky day’ there was no match that would fit within the defined matchup window of 30 minutes. The best match in time is for all three locations with S2, however, the time difference varies between 48 minutes (for Huibertsgat) to 4 h 34 minutes (for Groote gat N).

Table 1. Example of acquisitions on 25th June 2019 of in situ mwtl data and S2 and S3 data. Times in UTC. Inv. stands for invalid pixel (e.g. on a surfacing tidal flat).

Location	In situ time	S3B time	S3A time	S2 time	In situ value	S3B	S3A	S2 pixel value	S2 3*3 pixel window	Min time diff
Rottumerplaat	n/a	09:53	10:32	10:50	n/a	10	16	9	9	n/a
Huibertsgat O	11:02	09:53	10:32	10:50	8	13	16	7	8	0:48 h
Bocht v W.	13:51	09:53	10:32	10:50	86	inv.	inv.	29	34*	2:01 h
Groote gat N	16:24	09:53	10:32	10:50	106	42	inv.	34	35	4:43 h

* 6 valid pixels

3.2 Effect of tide on SPM

SPM peaks at roughly 2 ½ h before low tide and 3 h before high tide (taken from the measurements of the turbidity sensor and water level, Figure 3), but this varies somewhat per day. Sometimes these two main peaks consist both of two smaller peaks, while in other tidal cycles there is one peak before high tide and one before low tide.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3. Comparison of SPM from turbidity sensor, WISPstation, satellites and the correlation with the tidal cycle over a week in November 2018 (a), in May 2019 (b) and in July 2019 (c). The tidal cycle is plotted on the second y-axis. Time: local winter time.

Figure 3 shows that SPM from the WISPstation and the turbidity sensor follow the same pattern. The turbidity sensor values are higher than those of the WISPstation and the satellites, which is according to expectations that the largest sediment loads are found closest to the bottom.

The WISPstation does not measure when it is dark, which results in missing about one tidal cycle each day; more in November than in May of July when the WISPstation' needed to charge a few hours via its solar panel before it started measuring.

3.3 Seasonal variation

SPM concentrations are largely influenced by tide and wind (Figure 3). However, a seasonal pattern is visible when all data are added to one time series plot of a year (Figure 4). In January-February concentrations are higher, in July and August the average concentrations are lower.

Figure 4. Time series of SPM over a year from measurement turbidity sensor, WISPstation, S2 and S3

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3.4 Spatial variability

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Figure 5 shows the true colour composites of S2 images during low tide at 23 April 2019 (a) and during high tide at 18 May 2019 (b); SPM maps retrieved from these (c, d) and SPM maps derived from S3 imagery acquired at the same dates (e, f). The image of May 18th suffers from slight cloud cover, which removes some visible surface. Other than that, on April 23rd clearly a number of tidal flats surface. These areas are flagged out as land, as well as some of the surrounding pixels which probably suffer from bottom visibility or such high SPM concentrations that according to the NDWI threshold they are considered as 'not water'.

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(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 5. True colour composites of S2 images around low tide at 23 April 2019 (a: 10:26 UTC) and during high tide at 18 May 2019 (b:10:40 UTC); SPM maps retrieved from these (c, d) and SPM maps derived from S3 imagery acquired at the same dates (e: 10:26 UTC, f:10:17 UTC).

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The spatial patterns of the SPM maps from both satellites are similar (Figure 5), however, much more details are visible in the S2 image (also see Figure 6). During low tide, water masses with higher concentrations are seen around the 'Bocht van Watum' area, while at the same time already clearer North Sea water is entering via the inlets between the islands. During high tide (March 18th) the concentrations are therefore overall lower. As already seen Figure 3, the absolute values derived from S2 are lower than those derived from S3. There are no in situ mwfl data for validation available on these days.

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Figure 6. Detail of the same SPM maps as in Figure 5, of 23 April 2019 from S2 (a) and S3 (b).

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Figure 6 shows a detail of the maps based on S2 and S3. Clearly, the S2 map provides a much more detailed view, including swirls over the shallow area extending north-west from the Bocht van Watum. In the S3 image less pixels are flagged as 'land' than in S2, while areas probably contain a mixture of surfacing tidal flat and water. The resulting concentrations in these pixels are therefore assumed to be too high.

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3.5 Atmospheric correction based on in situ reflectance

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Because of the difference between S2 and S3, where the values of S2 are systematically lower (e.g. Figure 4), especially in the more inner and most turbid part of the estuary,

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the Dollard (Figure 5), the surface reflectance from both satellite instruments after AC were compared for two days where both satellites and the WISPstation had a valid acquisition within a short time frame. Next, the AC was forced on the in situ reflectance of the WISPstation, and the resulting surface reflectance were compared for the same spots. Three locations were picked to analyze the AC differences. These points were picked in the middle of the channels, to avoid invalid pixels due to surfacing tidal flats. The first one is the measurement pole location, the second point is in the main channel close to the city of Delfzijl and the last image was in main channel in the Dollard.

While the surface reflectance in the vicinity of the measurement pole are similar for both satellites, the difference becomes larger in the more turbid areas (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Remote sensing reflectances at the surface at three locations (top to bottom) and for two dates (left-right), after correction with C2RCC (without compensation for S3) – in black, and after forced AC – in grey, for S3 (straight lines) and S2 (dashed lines).

Following the C2RCC corrected reflectance from the clearer measurement pole location, via Delfzijl area to the most turbid Dollard area (Figure 7), the reflectance for S3 shows a large dip in the bands at 665, 673 and 681 nm, which is not seen at the measurement pole location, and it also not seen in the S2-C2RCC data. These spectral bands are

important for deriving Chlorophyll-a. On the other hand, the S2-C2RCC data becomes low in the blue-green range of the spectrum for the Dollard pixel of April 16th, and is for both days relatively low in the (N)IR wavelengths that are important for deriving SPM.

Time differences between the acquisitions were relatively small for these two days (For 16th of April: S2: 10:50, S3: 10:08, WISPstation: 11:00 for S2, 10:15 for S3; and for 18th of May: S2: 10:40 , S3A: 10:17, S3B: 09:38 , WISPstation: 10:45 for S2, 10:15 for S3A, 09:45 for S3B - all UTC). The WISPstation reading of 10:15 of 18/05/2019 was much higher than other reflectance in the same period, probably an outlier, affecting the S3A forced values of that day; therefore, these were left out of the analysis. When the AC was forced on the WISPstation, the dip in the S3 data of the Delfzijl and Dollard areas disappeared and the reflectance in the 665-681 nm range became similar to those of S2. Also the reflectance in the (N)IR are slightly elevated. The reflectance in the blue-green of the image of April and the (N)IR of both S2 images were elevated, becoming more similar to those of S3.

The calculated SPM for these days and both AC methods is shown in Table 2. Especially in the Dollard, the derived concentrations increase after applying a forced AC. In the area of the measurement pole the concentrations from both methods are already relatively similar and they do not change much.

Table 2. Calculated SPM for the reflectances as shown in Figure 7.

Location	16 th April				18 th May			
	S2-C2RCC	S2-Forced	S3-C2RCC	S3-Forced	S2-C2RCC	S2-Forced	S3-C2RCC	S3-Forced
Pole	23.2	17.9	12.6	14.3	9.8	8.6	9.8	9.2
Delfzijl	55.8	45.3	46.8	57.8	18.6	19.1	24.4	24.6
Dollard	43.5	58.8	58.3	70.7	35.3	43.4	37.1	43.3

The difference between the behavior of the C2RCC AC's for S2 and S3 SPM explain the differences in SPM concentrations over the Eems estuary, with similar values from both instruments in the area of the measurement pole, and increasingly different reflectances and derived concentrations in the more turbid areas.

3.6 Spatio-temporal variability

S3 captures the area almost every day, except for periods with cloud cover, which allows to follow the spatial variability over time. Since the timing of the tidal phases shift with about 30 minutes per day, and S3 always passes by in the morning between certain times, and the concentrations SPM vary based on the current velocity and their source, a cloud-free period can show the spatial variation in SPM as an effect of tidal change. In Figure 8 a series of images is shown, in which tidal effects can be followed.

Figure 8. Time series of S3 based SPM maps over a cloud free period, showing the spatio-temporal effects of the tidal cycle

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On April 15th the tide is low in the inner part of the Ems estuary. On this day, the Dollard area (in the red circle) is almost completely surfacing. From April 16th onwards, it is visual how the flood brings relatively clear North Sea water via the gullies between the islands (the small Rottumerplaat and the larger Borkum), passing by the in situ stations Rottemerplaat 3km and Huiberstgat oost, and from the north side of Borkum (see the red arrows). In April 17th, the relatively clear water is already seen deeper into the estuary (see the red arrow). On April 19th, the Dollard area is full of water (red circle), it is high tide. On the following days, we can see the ebb tide resuspending material into plumes that move northwards. On e.g. April 22nd, there is a clear ‘plume’ originating from the shallow area on the German (north-eastern side) of the estuary, moving with the ebb tide towards the Wadden Sea (red arrows). The spatial maps also show that the tidal phase is not the same over the whole area, and currents on the eastern side of the estuary are not always the same as on the western side. For example, on April 17th, there is ingoing tide on the eastern part of the estuary (arrow), but on the western part there are already plumes caused by the outgoing tide visible at the same location as the arrows of April 22nd. These kind of insights can only be studied in detail with satellite imagery.

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4. Discussion

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The SPM values from the WISPstation and the two satellite sensors were found to be lower than the SPM measurements from the turbidity sensor, which can be explained by the measurement depth (surface versus -3.5 meter NAP): closer to the bottom the concentrations SPM are higher due to resuspension (e.g. [19]).

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The rhythm with two main peaks that we found here agrees with literature [19,20], although the timing varies between the areas: [20] measured in the a tidal inlet in the east-west oriented part of the German Wadden Sea maxima of SPM one hour before slack tide, with higher maxima before high tide than before low tide. In the north-south oriented part of the German Wadden Sea [19] measured maxima ~ 2-4 h before slack time (reading from their Figure 2). Also neap tide and spring tide and wind influence the amount resuspended material [21]. Long-term and high-frequent measurements are needed to follow the tidal patterns over time.

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SPM concentration fluctuations are largely caused by tidal changes and wind. However, since stronger winds tend to occur in autumn and winter, while in these periods less stabilizing factors from benthic organisms are present, average concentrations are expected to be higher in autumn and winter than in spring and summer [5].

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The patterns seen in maps based on S2 and S3 are similar for the two satellite sensors (Figure 5), but S2 values are generally lower (Figure 2). A small portion of the variability between S2 and S3 might be explained by the influence of the measurement pole itself.

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Because the measurement pole is quite a large structure, it is also visible on S2 imagery, but not on S3. The pixel SPM values around the pole are much more variable than for other pixels in the surroundings. Especially one of the pixels north of the pole tends to have slightly lower SPM concentrations than the surroundings; this could be caused by lower reflectance values due to shadowing by the pole construction.

In some parts of the estuary that are much more turbid (Dollard), the C2RCC atmospheric correction method seems to be less accurate and behave differently for the two satellite sensors, leading to insecurity about the resulting concentrations in these areas. However, due to (almost) missing matchups of satellite with in situ data, this needs further research. The method to force the AC based on a single in situ measurement was tested as a potential solution, however, in the current set up it assumes the atmosphere over the whole area to be identical. Over such a large area, that is not realistic. However, the method shows the potential to improve AC methods over extremely turbid and complex waters.

A consideration when working with optical data, from either WISPstation or satellite, is that they cannot observe the large sediment load that passes by on the deeper water layers. To obtain a complete insight in sediment loads in a system, it would therefore be the best to combine satellite based maps and high-frequent measurements with measurements in a deeper layer (such as the turbidity sensor in this study) or over the whole water column. Drawback of those instruments is biofouling, something that does not happen to above-water instruments such as the WISPstation.

High sediment loads during winter might be less captured by all methods. In winter there are fewer measurements of the WISPstation due to a lack of sunlight, and fewer by satellite images because of cloud cover. However, due to wind, the manual in situ sampling can barely be carried out and cleaning of in-water sensors is also not done frequent enough. Also for the winter, the combination of all techniques might lead to most insights in the system. By comparing concentrations from different methods and interpreting the satellite-based maps, it is essential to take the tidal phase into account since the tidal variability on one spot (Figure 3) is very high compared to the spatial (Figure 8) and seasonal variability (Figure 4).

5. Conclusions

High-frequent automated measurements such as those from the turbidity sensor and the WISPstation are very relevant to study sediment fluxes over longer periods. Satellite images can provide the spatial-temporal insights that are needed to follow SPM patterns in a complex area such as an estuary. Overview maps can provide insights in tidal currents and movements of suspended matter that are impossible to obtain with in situ data. This information is essential for studying primary production in the water column and the related carrying capacity of this nature area. However, there is space for improvement, especially on the atmospheric correction methods for the most turbid areas. Forcing the atmospheric correction based on in situ reflectance could be an option. In such a case, it is advised to use multiple in situ instruments and to interpolate the atmospheric effects between the in situ stations before application to a satellite image.

We conclude that innovative methods, such as combining high-frequent and high-spatial measurements provide very good insights in the spatial and temporal variability in this complex estuary. Although there is space for improvements – especially for the most turbid areas – remains, the tested methods together can be applied in operational monitoring of this and other complex coastal areas.

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Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Appendix A Glossary

Q_w	Water leaving reflectance	450
Q_{sky}	air–sea interface reflection coefficient	451
AC	Atmospheric Correction model	452
C2RCC	Case 2 Regional Coast Colour atmospheric correction algorithm	453
CDOM	Coloured dissolved organic matter	454
Chl-a	Chlorophyll-a	455
Ed	Downwelling radiance	456
EO	Earth Observation	457
L_d	Downwelling radiance reflectance	458
L_u	Upwelling radiance reflectance	459
L_w	Water leaving radiance	460
mwtl	in situ locations of the Dutch national monitoring program	461
NIR	near-infrared	462
Rrs	remote sensing reflectance	463
S2 (A/B)	ESA Sentinel 2 satellite, there is an A and an B version of the instrument	464
S3 (A/B)	ESA Sentinel 3 satellite, there is an A and an B version of the instrument	465
SPM	Suspended Particulate Matter	466
WFD	EU Water Framework Directive	467
WISPstation	Water Insight spectrometer station	468

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